

REMUNERATION AND RESISTANCE FOR BAJO FISHERMEN IN ARU ISLANDS DISTRICT

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Abstract

In fishing communities, three social classes live side by side and fight for their own class but differ in diametrically different interests, namely local capital owners (ship owners), ship owners and ship crews. These differences have an impact on the distribution of wages that are not fair to the crew of the boat. This reality creates resistance between classes that is very difficult to break. This study uses a qualitative method with an ethnographic approach. This research was conducted in Dobo City, Aru Islands Regency, Maluku Province. The type of data consists of primary data and secondary data. Primary data was collected through observation, in-depth interviews and collective interviews Focus Group Discussion (FGD). While secondary data is obtained by searching literature sourced from printed books, ebooks, online and printed journals. Management and presentation of data is carried out by means of data reduction, data analysis, holistic-integrative presentation of data and drawing conclusions. The results showed that the crew of the boat on the Bajo fishermen cooperated so that hidden resistance occurred because of the unfair distribution of wages by the ship owner by moving to another boat, selling the catch in secret and credit to the bank to build a boat. The resistance that occurs is largely determined by the knowledge, feelings and suffering of labor fishermen as a substantial factor to respond to and evaluate the reality of the division of wages because they have suffered too long or live in the frame of dehumanization.

Keywords: Resistance, Fishermen, Domination, Social Class.

A. INTRODUCTION

Fishermen are basically able to prosper, but plans to become prosperous always fail because of the unequal distribution of income and inhumane regulatory controls. To escape from tight control, fishermen enter and engage in elements of interaction, such as desires, tendencies, affections, and feelings that ignite the fire of resistance, as moral sentiments that must be viewed as expressions of social life.

There is an interesting phenomenon in fishing communities that summarizes important and fundamental issues. The underlying assumption is that resistance always has dialectical implications for understanding social processes as complex interactions between human actors and social structures in which there is not only a symbiotic relationship but a relationship that is not mutually beneficial.

In the fishing community, three social classes live side by side and fight for their own class but differ in diametrically different interests so that it creates resistance. These groups are laborers (sawi), boat voters (punggawa) and capital owners (ship owners). This phenomenon is largely determined by knowledge, feelings and attitudes that last for a long time which are predisposing factors to respond to and evaluate social reality.

Holton (1992) stated that the reality of the relationship between classes in fishing communities was initially reciprocal and exploitative redistribution became an inherent factor in the emergence of resistance (1). The fishing community, which understands its existence as the oppressed, is awakened by the conflict that occurs between the class of capital owners (ship owners) and fishermen. The history of the fishing community essentially produces an emancipatory society, at the stage of its development, there is no longer exploitation in the fishing community and everyone can work according to their abilities and get everything they want.

Everything that happens in society is basically caused by deterministic economic relations. Society as an arena where gaps exist in it have the potential to cause conflict. Conflicts can occur between and between groups not limited to the type and size such as clans, tribes, families and countries.

The conflict is a major element in political and social change. Fishing communities are even formed from conflicts between major groups, focusing on the forces in society that promote competition and change. Fishermen or social class that has power, trying to control the class that does not have power. Relationships between fishing groups and boat owners fueled competition for scarce marine resources using power and wealth.

Giles and Evans (1986), competition between groups can manifest in the form of discrimination to occupy positions and social status (2). When a group gains control over community resources, they tend to maintain rules and laws to protect their interests. This encourages resistance, when groups without power try to gain access to the resources they want, resulting in unavoidable social change.

Social changes that often occur are beneficial to society, although sometimes they take place accompanied by violence. Resistance between crew members and ship owners is a universal phenomenon, as social inequality is widening, while social consensus is a very rare phenomenon.

Class resistance that occurs always has a very basic economic motive and continues to the desire to gain power and prestige as a motive for practical purposes. Russell (1988), if the minority has held a monopoly of power, it will gradually lead to slavery or servitude (3). In addition, the dynamics of the resistance of ship crews and ship owners occur in several arenas of substantive specialization such as fishermen's organizations and fishing communities experiencing revitalization such as collective behavior, social movements, inter-ethnic relations, stratification, and politics.

The resistance that occurs, as an acknowledgment that social reality is organized based on the unequal distribution of values and resources, such as material welfare, power and prestige which systematically increases tensions between community groups. Such special conditions increase the escalation of various forms of resistance between those who have values and resources and those who do not.

These conditions result in fishermen's awareness being subordinated to their interests in changing existing inequalities. However, for the sake of freedom, fishermen have to experience long oppression, and from the existence of a more organized subordinate, resistance and closed violence are created that require negotiation and compromise between crew members and ship owners. Fishermen who are not successful in making arrests will leave a lot of debt, so the ship owners are very disappointed because it will have an impact on excessive debt. This reality is separated from the expectations of the crew so that it opens up opportunities for resistance. In this situation, fishermen form a clear accumulated resistance to get out of the domination and hegemony of the shipowners.

Essentially, boat crews live in an arena of open conflict against ship owners and compete for economic, cultural and political dominance. The phenomenon of the contestation of dominance occurs in the social stratification system which is the main characteristic of organizing society, especially with a view that shows the degree of social strata. In general, the resistance that occurs between crew members and ship owners emphasizes the internal characteristics of the community. From the suffering experienced by fishermen and social interests that conflict with the reality of fishermen so that the crew of the boat always experience being subordinated. The ship owner is always dominant and maintains his dominance, either through persuasion or coercion of the crew to comply with the rules and fulfill their obligations.

The boat crew's resistance to the ship owners is supported by the world view that "in order to prosper, humans must work optimally to earn profits". Therefore, the reality of the life of the crew of the boat who can no longer coexist with the owner of the ship cannot be seen as a static system of meaning, but must be seen in conditions and struggles that are constantly changing and capable of articulating various interests. From this struggle, it can be said that the ship owners have won the economic battle, but have oppressed the crew so that they fight and compete for resources.

The character of resistance also leads to the consequences and implications of the Bajo fisherman's way of thinking to understand the political and ideological character and characteristics that are consistently held by ship owners. Fishermen's attention is also on political transformation due to social and political tensions caused by the process of economic restraint that stimulates or limits the economic and political role of fishing groups and boat crews. Until now, what stands out is that the autonomy of the boat owners is more dominant, but it is difficult to face the hidden resistance of the boat crew.

By looking at this reality, there are various characteristics of the development and dominance of the ship owner over the crew of the boat that has attracted my attention to study it holistically and meaningfully. From the resistance of the boat crew, it is essentially an emancipatory movement to escape from the entanglements of the shipowners which has implications for progressive actions to achieve prosperity. This paper reveals three realities of resistance between crew members and ship owners, namely the forms of relations between ship crews and ship owners, forms of domination of ship owners over crew members, and weapons of resistance like boat crews against ship owners domination.

B. LITERATURE REVIEW

Research on resistance in fishing communities has been carried out by various researchers, including: Atamimi et al (2018), mastery of production tools is a portrait of fishermen's suffering (4). Kusnadi (2016), the penetration of capitalism in fishing communities supported by fisheries modernization policies is a fundamental factor causing the scarcity of fishery resources and decreasing catch productivity (5). Ertor (2020), the political climate that is not in favor of the fishing community, the presence of capitalists, fishermen's cooperatives which are legitimized by the state and discrimination of capital owners have led to fishermen's resistance (6). Arrazie (2020), the government's weakness in enforcing maritime law, so that fishermen fight back because they suffer losses from decreased catches, damage to fishing gear and decreased income (7). Arief (2021), fishermen are helpless because of the penetration of capitalism in the aspects of capital and technology (8).

C. RESEARCH METHOD

a. Types of research

This research uses an ethnographic method that seeks to study cultural events about the genealogy of resistance between crew members against the domination of ship owners. This research is also based on the phenomenon of the crew of the boat who do not submit or disobey the power of the ship owner. This research was conducted in a natural situation, so there is no limit in interpreting or understanding the phenomenon under study. The selection of the ethnographic method is very appropriate to describe the reality that is not based solely on the interpretation of the researcher but from the ritual actors themselves or by "seeing reality from the perspective of the perpetrator, namely the mental component in the minds of those who are members of a culture or society, who see themselves as themselves and the world from their own perspective, on the basis of the values, knowledge and attitudes that are nurtured in the culture.

Therefore, the ethnographic method becomes very interesting and can provide added value in scientific studies because it describes the diversity of complex conceptual structures of cultural phenomena as they are and explores the events or contexts represented in the narrative as situations that actually occur or are contextual in nature with the aim of to describe holistically the culture of Bajo fishermen who keep and hide cultural actors in carrying out resistance actions.

b. Research sites

This research was conducted in the city of Dobo, Aru Islands district because this area is very high in resistance between crew members and boat owners. So far, the presence of the Bajo people in the city is considered a symbol of the strength of the maritime economy because they dare to sail the seas by boat to carry out fishing activities. Their intensity in sailing and looking for marine products in the form of sea cucumbers, fish and shells is the main attraction for ship owners to provide capital to the crew with a persuasion mechanism.

However, after a long time the interaction took place, slowly but surely the crew began to realize that the kindness that had been given by the boat owner was full of interests and was hiding in false rhetoric and logic. Through the politics of imagery which is increasingly revealing its reality, the crew of the ship carried out covert resistance and improved adaptation in various ways, one of which was buying shipping and fishing needs from Bugis, Makassarese and Javanese people who owned shops. This action was taken to get a cheap price because buying or borrowing from ship owners who act as shop owners and buyers of seafood in the city of Dobo is always at a low price.

However, when it was discovered by the boat owners, they fought back by carrying out strict monitoring or control, confiscated Bajo fishing boats and compromised with fellow boat owners and local boat owners so as not to give space to crew members whose names were registered as fishermen who have bad image for not buying shipping and catching necessities.

c. Research Informants

Research informants vary widely, namely boat crew and boat voters. These informants were chosen deliberately and their real names were changed to pseudonyms with the consideration that they know and understand the reality of the resistance that has been going on and keep them from potential control from neighbors or other fishermen because they have provided information about their situation and condition and their potential to do resistance.

d. Data Sources and Data Collection Techniques

This research is supported by data derived from primary data through observation and in-depth interviews. First, observation is done by direct observation and systematic recording of the object to be studied. When making observations, the instrument is a camera to photograph the activities of Bajo fishermen and boat owners.

Second, in-depth interviews were conducted to determine the attitudes, behaviors and ways of thinking of the crew and ship owners. Interviews will use various data collection instruments in the form of interview guidelines in the form of questions developed during the study, recording conversations using cellphones and using field notes to briefly describe the context of behavior, the informant's feelings, reactions to experiences that have been passed and brief reflections on personal meanings. and the meaning of the event.

In addition to primary data, this study also uses secondary data as supporting data to understand research issues related to the attitudes, behaviors and ways of thinking of ship crews and ship owners sourced from books and research journals that have been conducted by previous researchers and published online or published in print.

e. Data analysis technique

The steps to analyze the data that have been obtained that have been conceptualized by the informants are carried out by ethnography, firstly, transcribing the data obtained from in-depth interviews stored in interview recordings and field notes. The second step is to read the entire data and then detect the emerging themes and sort them into parts as conceptualized by the informant to be the topic of discussion.

Third, a detailed analysis of thematic segments which refer to a systematic examination of something to determine its parts, the relationship between the parts and the whole and interpret them to make it possible to find various problems and find the cultural meaning of the actions of resistance carried out by Bajo fishermen against their owners. boat. Fourth, describe holistically-integratively in order to get a native's point of view of everything found on the topic, research focus and integrate it with the domain of relevant theoretical ideas.

D. DISCUSSION

Currently, no one can dispute the superiority of the power of the boat owner because it dominates the fishermen's economic system. In almost every sector of life, the logic and culture of ship owners are present to drive activities. The criticisms directed at the ship owner by the crew actually lead to the co-optation of these criticisms to further confirm the boat owner as a superior person. Below, I will present the power relations between the crew and ship owners, the domination, control and resistance of fishermen in an adequate and deep manner.

1. Relation of power of ship crew and ship owner

The progress of consciousness, science and technology that is increasingly rapidly in the twentieth century actually makes humans even more inhumane. This reality occurs because of the possession of power that is able to control and control behavior, ethics, and manners. Because of power, human behavior is restrained and even silenced. Resistance to any general attempt to hide identity radiates widely through modern knowledge and technology created, composed of a complex and diverse, distinctive, and oppressive discourse network. So, what is happening now is a stimulus that is more than one (polymorph), structured and massive.

Foucault uncovers from all corners of human behavior. It offers a procedure that makes it possible to tell the truth based on power and knowledge. For Foucault (2002), power always has implications for knowledge and vice versa. He argues that the power lies in the strategy that is operated at every level (9).

Wianti et al (2012), the production orientation of fishermen who are under pressure from ship owners aims to meet market needs to achieve profits (10). Until now, the crew of the ship directly experienced economic and socio-cultural obstacles because they lost their existence as human beings who were free to determine their attitude in dealing with local traders.

In the past we never had a fight with the ship owners because they were very nice. Every major religious event (Eid al-Fitr and Eid al-Adha) they always give gifts to the ship's crew. We also believe that we must replace this kindness with loyalty in the form of selling seafood to them (Muaz, 46 years old).

The kindness of the shipowners became the stimulus for the movement that merged into collective action, including the tactic of giving gifts. The goal is to seek and find the sympathy of the crew in the community so that they can be mobilized and join the ship owners. In this context, family units, friendship networks, volunteer associations, are slowly formed.

So, power is not a monopoly of a certain group or class, however, power is productive, it will even produce knowledge and sympathy from subjects or fishermen that it meets regularly. The reality of the kindness of ship owners is the basic source of framing because they have the ability and political opportunity as well as mobilization, resources and even hacking fishermen's complaints, preventing rifts and cultural contradictions.

According to Heilbroner (1991) the notion of capital as a social relationship reveals the essence of that relationship, namely domination. The domination relationship has two poles. First, the social dependence of the powerless on the owners of capital and without that dependence capital has no effect. Second, the relentless and insatiable urge to accumulate capital (11).

This drive is driven by the desire for prestige and prominence (self-realization). This unsatisfied drive to accumulate wealth is a manifestation of self-actualization. However, this affective need is only a necessary condition that is not yet a sufficient condition for the drive to pursue wealth. Wealth gives its owner the ability to direct and mobilize the activities of society using wealth as an inseparable social category.

Thus, the essence of the ship owner who hides in the mode of goodness, is the relentless and unsatisfactory urge to accumulate capital as a sublimation of the subconscious urge of humans to realize themselves, dominate, rule. Because this urge is rooted in human identity, the ship owner is more of a mode of human existence. Perhaps this is why the boat owners are able to survive and increasingly become the hegemony of the fishing community.

Furthermore, the elements contained by ship owners so that power relations become increasingly massive are that there are several strengths that allow ship owners to survive until now through various sharp criticisms and obstacles. First, the adaptability and transformation of ship owners is very high, so that they are able to absorb and modify every criticism and obstacle from fishermen to strengthen their existence. For example, how is the threat of a fishermen's rebellion not being realized, because on the one hand, fishermen experience freezing critical awareness (reification), and on the other hand, boat owners provide "kindness" to fishermen with the concept of "modes of kindness". In turn, shipowners obtain consent to dominate fishing communities through economic, political and cultural hegemony or as Heilbroner puts it that capital regimes have the ability to gain mass obedience by generating economic "patriotism".

Second, the high adaptability and power relations of shipowners can be traced to the time inherent in the nature of shipowners, namely the drive for power and self-realization through wealth. Based on these reasons, among others, Berger (1990) is willing to bet that the future of the world economy is in the hands of capitalists. Third, the cultural creativity of the capitalist owner and his capacity to absorb ideas and tolerance for various thoughts (12).

Individual freedom and rights provide space for humans to innovate and work for the sake of achieving survival and happiness. With this premise, Murchland (1992) confidently hopes that the owners of capital will be able to spread humanism that can save human civilization in the future even if they have to sacrifice other humans (13).

2. Form of domination of ship owners and stimulus of resistance

The reality of the gap and the dominance of ship owners over fishermen has become a stimulus for change, because the image that is widely accepted by fishermen as powerless people. These destructive forms are unavoidable which tend to occur continuously and contribute to a number of exponents, namely the decomposition of capital, work morale, decomposition of labor, and the growth of the fishermen's social class which is not essentially a homogeneous class, but is structured in a complex hierarchy of power. This process improves the welfare of fishermen in part because they carry out high mobility and maximum fishing practices and do not want to sell their catch to boat owners who have long existed as economic rulers and hold the role of patron.

Sudarmono et al (2012), the social structure (patron-client) formed in fishing communities has created fishermen (clients) in the lowest position, thus creating resistance (14). Dahrendorf (1959), said that conflict in society is a condition that cannot be separated because of inter-class interests in the hierarchy of power and authority (15). In line with this view, in fishing communities there are various mechanisms that have been developed to reduce and control resistance or prolonged conflict. As a result, resistance does not develop into a disruptive one because the fishermen's revolutionary actions try to dismantle the domination of the ship owners to be present in the consciousness of emancipation achieved by struggle.

So far, they control fishermen because they bind fishermen by giving loans and providing fishing and fishing needs. The gift also binds fishermen so they cannot interact with other traders because it can hinder them from seeking profit (Suandi, 52 years old).

Ship owners who act as capital owners who live from profits and control of resources create exploitation and exploitation of humans over humans. The magnitude of the structural role of ship owners rather than fishermen's awareness and morality, the implication is not changes that end resistance but changes in economic structure due to conflicts of interest between fishermen and ship owners. These attitudes and actions are the basis for creating progressive-revolutionary changes from fishermen to fight the status quo and oppose any changes in the power structure.

According to Scott (1990: 1), from the struggle for profit and the status quo, capitalists have been and will always act through the decency and coercion that has been imposed throughout history (16). Such a pattern is required of the shipowner subject to be described and systematic forms of social subordination i.e. worker to shipowner, charterer or cultivator to landlord, servant to master, member of the subject race to one of the dominant races. With rare, but significant exceptions in the will of subordinates, due to prudence, fear, and the desire to curry favor, support, is formed to attract the strong expectations of subordinates and those who dominate.

Any progress in fishing society can only be achieved in a revolutionary movement. All of that, leads to the final aspired goal, namely "to escape from domination and achieve prosperity". The fact that Bajo fishermen (the crew of the ship) have determined their own destiny in the shadow of the ship owner is not a coincidence, but a human effort to improve life by holding a

fishermen's political organization with the principle of social justice. Furthermore, the fishermen's resistance believes that to understand the history and direction of change, it is not necessary to pay attention to what other people think but how to work and reproduce. Thus, the way fishermen work and produce will determine what fishermen think.

Through resistance and hard work, fishermen can determine the economic value of a commodity—fish as a catch—can be determined objectively. In the sense that, fishermen get wages that are worth to restore their condition and the needs of their families. All social changes from resistance that exist in fishing communities occur through collective consciousness which is determined by an economic material basis. Therefore, the failure or success of fishermen is largely determined by the economic value.

Failures that occur can become prejudices or negative attitudes directed at Bajo fishermen (the crew). Johnson (1986), prejudice can occur because of the picture of group differences, capitalist cultural values that consider superior and other races inferior and accompanying stereotypes. This attitude becomes a symptom of resistance, it contains thoughts and resistance that are not utopian but tactical, so that reality gives birth to drastic changes or undergoes continuous dialectical changes.

The changes that have occurred were born from a form of joint action that aims to carry out social reorganization, both neatly organized and in a fluid and informal manner. The movement is a collective challenge based on the common goals of a sense of social solidarity and ongoing social interaction between opposing elites and those in power.

There are two sides that stand out from the resistance, namely, first, organized efforts to bring about changes in fishermen's institutions through social movements that involve collective challenges. These challenges often focus on common interests or are directed as a benchmark for initiating broader changes in the structure of social institutions and politics of social security distribution and conceptualization of social and political rights and responsibilities. Both resistances have a political purpose in that they involve changes in the distribution of power and authority. These political goals can only be achieved through ongoing interactions with political actors outside the movement, the most important of which are allies and political rivalries and power authorities, namely ship owners who are considered capitalists.

The impact and loss of the authority and policy of ship owners regarding confiscating fishing boats have been used as a trigger for fishermen to carry out a resistance. The propaganda element is part of the fishermen's closed resistance “don't sell marine products to ship owners. Scott (1985), explains that propaganda that usually occurs in small fights is in the form of arguments that symbolize and label the events that are being felt and happening. Fishermen think that the policy of ship owners is a negative model of the ruling class that has disrupted social order (17).

The difference in perception between fishermen and boat owners makes a difference in how to respond in a contest of resistance. The different socioeconomic status of fishermen also influences their attitude in assessing the impacts and losses that are always experienced by fishermen. Labor fishermen will usually complain more because they feel very disadvantaged

because they see a new phenomenon of shipowner domination with a high level of economic growth and development dominated by ship owners, and with their awareness that with their current socio-economic characteristics and status, they do not will be able to match, and cannot also enter and participate in the welfare agenda.

Ship owners in the Aru Islands district act as moral authority holders and control the basis of social relations and stability. Ship owners hide in a big agenda to prosper themselves and legitimize the social formation of ship owners in order to continue to exist. Thus, in order to achieve that goal, the ship owner must have the ability to fulfill the moral imperative that has been held for a long time, namely to become rich, the ship owner must grasp it.

However, fishermen do not remain silent and assume that the will of prosperity does not have to be centered on the owner of the ship, but lies with everyone. However, welfare is taken away and monopolized by the ship owner so that the crew as the lower class are unable to make a historical leap to achieve prosperity due to fraud in determining the price of fishing needs and the price of marine products.

In my opinion, it is the problem of social injustice that has led to the rise of the crew of the ship's resistance movement. Social injustice is a derivation and is influenced by three important elements in each element in the social system, namely social coordination, or power, division of labor and distribution of goods. These two things are always evaluated in terms of the ability to provide protection to citizens and maintain peace and order in society.

3. Activity control and Hierarchical supervision

Bajo fishermen realized that the ship's owner had arrived at the door to glory. Bajo fishermen have a perception of existing behavioral alternatives and are increasingly trying to explain that the behavioral consequences that are imagined in an action, affect the collective consciousness of fishermen and increasingly allow actions to be followed by other individuals.

With the intensity of the ship owner's control, the desire of Bajo fishermen will be increasingly seen in strong collective action and involvement in social movements. Foucault (82: 1997) shows how discipline also touches the body through activity control achieved by setting time, establishing timeliness with action, creating efficient postures, creating efficient relationships, and increasing time effectiveness (18).

In monitoring activities, there are three important patterns carried out by ship owners, namely the formation of a regular rhythm, mastery of busyness, and regulation of repetition actions. With this control, the ship owner is able to place the crew of the boat to be controlled or monitored at any time.

We are aware that we are being monitored by the ship's owner's confidant. They even always came to visit us when we got home or after making an arrest. They always ask how many fish were found, possibly how many kilograms of the current catch, and bribe the crew of the boat to answer their questions (Jumadil, 38 years old, Fikram 47 years old and Samsul 39 years old).

The monitoring technique for Bajo fishermen (the crew) was originally carried out through other people or people hired to monitor fishermen's activities to make them known and make them obey. This is to facilitate actions that allow close and continuous observation or monitoring. The monitoring is careful and specific through which the subject being mastered functions more intensively.

According to Foucault (1997:97), the application of discipline presupposes the existence of a coercive mechanism through supervision that cannot be seen by the monitoring party (invisible). Discipline uses a technique that allows him to see the effects of the power he wields without being able to be seen by those who are subject to the power. From here comes the technique of 'monitoring' which prepares new knowledge about humans (18).

4. The boat crew's weapon of resistance against the domination of the ship owner

In the history of resistance and obedience of the ruled or oppressed classes, humans are often depicted as objects whose entire activity is limited by a shackled structure. That is, there is no place at all for humans to act as subjects who have their own authority. Even though it is proven that the existence of an oppressed class such as fishermen is not always in an equal position, but on the contrary they are also able to make their own history.

Failure to carry out mutual obligations between boat owners and fishermen will lead to anger or social rift. Thus, resistance to the power of the ship owner will occur because the ship owner as the authority holder is no longer able to fulfill his basic moral obligations, namely being honest and fair. The social inequalities that occur are inherent with fishermen's resistance to self-determination and creating new harmony. The ultimate goal is to keep the boat containing the engine and fishing gear as the most valuable treasure.

Fishermen basically have to try to compensate for the contradictions or social inequalities that have occurred so far. Foucault sees social reality as a discursive field, which is a competition of various meanings and the organization of institutions and social processes that are given meaning through distinctive ways. Knowledge must be explained based on institutions and events that take place in institutions, whether they are technical, economic, social, or political. But the institutions themselves cannot function without power. For this reason, Foucault conducts an analysis of power that is institutional—not personal. But unlike the Marxists, Foucault did not study power in a process mechanism. Power is not seen as the embodiment or logical consequence of economic ownership, but simply as a strategy to carry out something.

The term strategy is meant not a group of individuals in carrying out an action, but "the impact of a strategic position." The types of power do not function or function the meaning of action or speech, because the provisions for action can be formed directly without going through an intermediary of meaning. The problem raised by Foucault is that the mastery process is not the result of conscious motivation or subconscious motivation. Power or power basically does not limit groups or individuals to impose their will on other parties, and power is fundamental to all social interactions in fishermen's lives.

With the power of ship owners that I have experienced so far, it requires me to muster up the strength to fight back by inviting family and friends of fishermen not to depend on the owner of the ship because so far we have not been treated as fishermen who should be prosperous but our welfare is hampered by the owner. ship for confiscating the boat because it was unsuccessful in making the arrest. Even though not being successful in catching fish is not entirely the crew's fault, it could be a bad fishing season (Tantui, 48 years old).

The descriptive epistemic idea by Bajo fishermen becomes a historical conception of the emergence of a new epistemic configuration that includes a new materialist consciousness. Bajo fishermen think and relate as a result of the so-called “endless repeating drama of domination” that is human history. Bajo fishermen want to be the determinants of their economic life by mobilizing the power contained in the fishing community as a whole.

The reality that has been happening so far is that there are always clashes, between one group or class and another using one strategy and another. Foucault's dictum states that power and knowledge are closely related to each other. Knowledge will be possible to develop outside the realm of power, between knowledge and power there is a relationship that develops each other. There is no practice of exercising power which does not give rise to knowledge, and there is no knowledge in which there is no power relation.

Foucault analyzes the relation of power and knowledge based not on the 'subject' of knowledge that is free or not free from the relation of the power system, but on the contrary, views that both the subject who knows, the object that is known and the way knowledge occurs are the fundamental consequences of power relations in knowledge. . So it is not the activity that produces the body of knowledge, but the relation between power and knowledge.

The exercise of the power of the ship owner in the form of confiscation of fishing boats because they are unable to pay their debts can marginalize fishermen. Thus, punishment as a complex social function. Punishment as a political strategy and as a technique is spread in society and appears in broader and general ways of exercising power.

The resistance that occurs is understood as a response to a change initiative, a response to stimuli that shape reality. In the face of various pressures, the ship owners severely limit the space for the crew's movement because every maneuver is always considered very dangerous and threatens the stability of the ship owner.

Essentially, there is a connection between the forms of subjugation of the body, mind, will, will, and impulses from the shipowners with the strategies of implementing punishment that are capable of giving birth to humans as objects of knowledge and body discipline. The relationship between the ruler (ship owner) and the controlled (ship crew) will eventually give birth to supervision and normalization as an embodiment of the principle of discipline.

Anderson (2008) in addition, mastery also occurs through procedures formed by capitalists by emphasizing primordial fatalities, language, reciprocal relations and arbitrary actions to control humans. The relationship seems harmonious but hides resistance from time to time (19).

Fishermen's resistance is characterized by several reasons, namely: first, collective challenges. Resistance is always marked by challenges to resist through disruptive direct action against elites of authority, other groups or certain cultural rules. Collective challenges are often characterized by acts of disrupting, obstructing, or creating uncertainty about the activities of other parties. On the other hand, the collective challenge is the most common characteristic of social movements. The fact that the movement carried out by the crew of the ship lacks stable resources because it does not get support from other fishermen. In approaching a new constitution and asserting their claims, opposition may be the only resources the movement can control, therefore the movement uses the collective challenge to become a focal point for supporters to gain the attention of the opposing camp and third parties and create a constituency for represented.

Second, the existence of an agenda to develop joint claims against opposing parties in authority or elites of shared values and interests is the basis of their actions. Third, Solidarity and Collective Identification. Something that jointly moves the fishermen's resistance is the participant's consideration of common interests which then drives the change from mere movement potential to real action by moving collective agreements. Movement plans play an important role in stimulating the emergence of such agreements, but leaders can only create an agreement. social movements when they dig deeper into feelings of solidarity or identity that stem from ethnicity.

Fourth, maintain the politics of resistance. Only by fostering collective action against the shipowners can a resistance become a social movement, collective goals of shared identity and identifiable challenges help the movement to maintain this politics of resistance otherwise if they are not able to maintain a common challenge then their movement will evaporate into individual anger. and collective because it maintains collective action in interaction with a strong adversary marks the shifting point where an opposition turns into a movement.

When the control is held by the economically strong class in society, repression from the ruling class is very likely to occur. The ruling class also exercises a hegemonic power that is able to perpetuate its power from the dominant class. Patria and Andi (2009), hegemony is always related to the preparation of forces to survive and carry out its ideological mission to the proletarian masses (20).

Scott (1985) also said that public demands that were not responded to in the end made fishing communities identified with poverty and low social status less likely to engage in open conflict (17). The fishing community will tend to carry out a form of closed resistance or what is commonly referred to as hidden transcript resistance. Resistance focuses on the material basis of class relations and class struggles, acting as both individual and collective acts of resistance as well as forms of ideological resistance that challenge the definition of the dominant situation and demand it as a standard of justice and fairness.

The expression of resistance is also entered into the form of symbolic resistance that fishermen do to the ship owner. A form of pure symbolic resistance, with malicious gossip talking about shipowners who don't use any respect at all. Behind every gossip story there is news, and an

implied statement about a rule that has been violated and the loss of humanist principles of shipowners (Scott, 1985).

E. CONCLUSION

The dominance of ship owners has added new problems for fishermen and has resulted in social, economic and physical losses for fishermen and triggers potential conflicts. Fishermen's resistance to boat owners always occurs because fishermen consider the use of unfair profit-sharing methods and buying cheap catches to be very unprofitable for fishermen. In addition, the boat confiscation mechanism has also become the forerunner of the anger of the crew, so they tend to sell their catch to other people in order to get more profit that can be used to pay off debts.

Because crew members always commit such fraudulent acts, ship owners do not remain silent, so they must use control and discipline methods to read the activities under their control (fishermen) by creating 'correction' and 'normalization' methods. Ship owners need a pattern of integration between control mechanisms by creating spies, namely placing individuals into rooms to monitor those who are controlled. This business produces a variety of important and accurate information to be evaluated in order to create order and benefit ship owners.

Fishermen who are monitored by comparing catches on a regular basis can be a basic reference for taking firm action against crew members. From the dialectic that occurs, fishermen experience dehumanization because they are unable to redefine and read the movements of ship owners, which change every time. Therefore, fishermen must perform resistance in order to avoid domination.

F. IMPLICATION/LIMITATION AND SUGGESTIONS

This research was carried out in a relatively short time so it really needs more in-depth research and explanations about the core problems of remuneration and resistance to Bajo Fishermen which have not been resolved so far. Therefore, further research is needed from other social science disciplines in order to find the core of the problem that can be used as a basic reference by academics and the government in solving fishermen's problems, especially regarding conflict, resistance and fishermen's welfare.

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